

Studies on induction of organic crystals in Wistar rat models and its interaction with *Withania somnifera*

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Abstract : The study was carried out to know the effect of in *Withania somnifera* to control the induced renal crystals in Wistar rats and also to know the effect of the induced chemical (ethylene glycol) in the metabolism of the tested animals. In this study the renal stones (crystals) were induced in the animals by introducing ethylene glycol and allow it to counteract with *Withania somnifera*. The main focus of this study was to determine the interaction between the *Withania somnifera* and the organic renal kidney stones in Wistar rats and the results showed that *Withania somnifera* has the curative effect in the formation of renal stones against ethylene glycol it may be due to the present of Withaferin A (an active constituent present in *Withania somnifera*).

Keywords : Withaferin A, renal stones, ethylene glycol, Wistar rats.

Introduction

Among various urologic disorders, renal crystals or kidney stones are most frequent and predominant one. These stones are formed due to the deposition of unwanted minerals in the kidney or urinary tract by consuming hard water which contains excess of calcium⁴. Process involved in stone formation is nucleation, aggregation and finally settled in the urinary tract³. This condition is medically termed as Urolithiasis¹. The main constituent of renal crystal is calcium oxalate. Specifically, calcium oxalate monohydrate, calcium oxalate dihydrate and calcium phosphate are most commonly occurring ones². Recently, kidney stones are treated by extracorporeal shockwave lithotripsy but recent research prevails that it leads to severe renal injury and decrease in renal function⁵. So our consideration is on phytotherapy which is natural, applicable and also an alternative traditional medicine. Many plants used to treat renal crystals such as *Hernaria hirsuta*, *Mimusop elengi* etc.⁶.

We carried out with an ayurvedic plant *Withania somnifera* which is also known as "Indian ginseng". Apart from the kidney stones they are used to treat paralysis, arthritis and it enhances the immune strength against many

diseases⁷. It because of the active organic compound present in *Withania somnifera* is Withaferin A which has the capacity to interfere and stop the calcium signalling in the renal crystals⁸. Hence, crystallization will cease. Therefore, this experiment was carried out on Wistar albino female rats through inducing renal crystals by administering the ethylene glycol orally which is the strong inducer of Urolithiasis in rats⁹. To know the interaction between the active compound Withaferin A and the renal crystals which is induced by ethylene glycol is the main focus of this study.

Materials and methods :

Animals :

14 Wistar albino female rats weighed approximately 150–200 g are authorized by Animal Ethics Committee (VIT/IAEC/VI/4).

Drug :

The drug (*Withania somnifera*) was brought from INCOPS Adayar, which was in powder form so dissolved in water and orally administered to rats.

Method :

The grouping of Wistar rats were done as follows :

Group 1 : It consists of two female rats which were fed with regular food and water. Group 2 : It consists of four female rats which were fed with normal food and water along with ethylene glycol (0.75%) for the induction of renal crystals. Group 3 : It consists of four female rats which were induced with (0.75%) of ethylene glycol along with its normal diet. *Withania somnifera* drug (400 mg/kg) was given after 15 days of the induction, to know the curative effect of the drug. Group 4 : It consists of 4 female rats which were fed with (0.75%) of ethylene glycol and *Withania somnifera* drug (400 mg/kg) simultaneously with normal feed to know the interaction between the Withaferin A and renal crystals¹⁰.

Group 1 : Control

Group 2 : Induced

Group 3 : Curative

Group 4 : Preventive

Histopathology analysis of kidney for antilithiatic activity :

Transverse section of kidneys was kept in 10% of formaldehyde solution. The tissues were then dehydrated and embedded in paraffin wax. The tissue sections were stained hematoxylin and eosin¹⁰ for histopathology analyses.

Results and discussion

Group 1 : Control

Group 2 : Induced

Group 3 : Curative

Group 4 : Preventive

The control group does not show any symptoms of disease since they were given plain water and normal feed. Induction of ethylene glycol in Group 2 animals lead to the increase in eosinophils count which may lead to renal calculi in future. In curative, rats were fed with *Withania somnifera* , which is a curative medicine, after the 15 days of oral administration of the ethylene glycol. It was clearly observed that the number of eosinophils were found to be decreasing. Finally in preventive, rats were first fed with *Withania somnifera* along with the ethylene glycol to determine the preventive effect of the drug. The eosinophils count were again found to be decreased.

According to the chemistry perspective, the *Withania somnifera* consists of 35 chemical constituent such as steroids, alkaloids, steroidal, lactones etc., Withaferin A is one of the steroidal lactones⁸. This has a main application in recovery of various broad numbers of diseases such as cancer, inflammation, cardiac weakness, ulcers, asthma and also acts as anti-stress factor, anti-oxidant activity, anti-carcinogenic activity, anti-aging activity, cardio protector activity, hypothyroid activity etc. and also series of investigations exhibit on animal models with *Withania*

somnifera it was found that it increases the count of white blood cells which is key factor of immunity. So it's also acts as immunoregulator and chemo protective agent. In our study we also found the eosinophils number is increased in the case of induced rats so it may be due to the cytotoxic effect of macrophages exposed to *Withania somnifera*⁸. Then it also has the capacity to interfere and to stop the calcium signalling between the renal crystals⁹. Thus this may be the effect of Withaferin A is preventing the formation of kidney stones.

Conclusion

From the above phytotherapy, it was clearly declared that it enhances the immunity especially white blood cells mainly eosinophils against the renal crystals so it has the efficiency to act as an effective phytomedicine for kidney stones and also many disorders.

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